

The Greek New Testament Conversion Project

Session 30-24 (joint session with Eep Talstra Centre for Bible and Computer and Hellenistic Greek Language and Linguistics)

- Willem Th. van Peursen, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and Oliver Glanz, Andrews University: The Greek TF Conversion Project
- Tony Jurg, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam: Navigating the Challenges in Creating Text Fabric Datasets (with Focus on the NT Greek Corpus)
- Saulo de Oliveira Cantanhêde, Andrews University: Coding the Greek New Testament in an Open Source Environment

FACULTY OF
RELIGION
AND THEOLOGY

Navigating the Challenges in Creating Text-Fabric Datasets

Tony Jurg, ETCBC/VU Amsterdam

This presentation

Share some highlights:

- How this projects was executed
- Key decision points
- Learnings that can benefit other projects

**NAVIGATING THE CHALLENGES
IN CREATING TEXT-FABRIC DATASETS**

TONY JURG
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands

SAULO DE OLIVEIRA CANTANHÊDE
Andrews University, Berrien Springs, MI, USA

Abstract

The established high-quality, annotated database of the Hebrew Bible created by the ETCBC enabled advanced linguistic analysis. The 'Greek New Testament Conversion Project,' started by the VU Amsterdam and Andrews University, aimed to create a comparable Text-Fabric dataset for the Nestle 1904 Greek New Testament.

A primary requirement was to implement constituency-based syntax trees, which involved transforming our source data's word-group structure into a syntactic one. Incorporating both the original and translated data, it facilitates the visualization of syntax trees in either format.

This article outlines the project's methodology, including defining requirements, selecting data sources, assessing data provenance, evaluating conversion methods, and creating documentation. The explicit purpose of this article is to aid similar future initiatives, concluding with a checklist.

'GNT TF Conversion Project' Objectives

Create a High-Quality Text-Fabric Dataset: a Text-Fabric dataset of the Greek New Testament that matches the usability and quality standards of the BHSA.

Comprehensive Documentation: quality end-user focused documentation demonstrating and unlocking the dataset potential.

Publications and Knowledge Sharing:

- **Conversion Project Insights:** An article accounting for the conversion process, process from both technical and organizational perspectives; highlighting successes, challenges, and lessons learned.
- **Dataset Overview:** An article with comprehensive description of the resulting database, enabling prospective users to grasp its core features and potential applications.
- **Educational Applications:** An article on how this Text-Fabric dataset can be utilized in educational settings, particularly for teaching Biblical Greek.
- **Syntactical Analysis:** An article on leveraging this Text-Fabric dataset for syntactical analysis in Biblical Greek studies, demonstrating its benefits for linguistic research.

Preliminary Considerations

First Question: Why pursuing this?

- Does it unlock new types of data previously unavailable?
- Does it enable or enhance original research options?
- Does it expand analytical possibilities?
- Does it make the data more accessible or easier to use?
- Will it increase your audience?
- Will it improve transparency, reproducibility and accountability
- Any other benefits of the data conversion?

For our project:

The primary benefit (or requirement) was to obtain a quality query and display function for syntax trees in a Greek New Testament Text-Fabric dataset that is open access and non-restrictive licensed.

Preliminary Considerations

Second Question: Is it worth the effort?

- Are the necessary resources such as funding, access to data, and time available for the conversion?
- Does the anticipated benefit justify the investment of resources?
- Can the project be sustained over time with the available resources?
- Are there any legal, ethical, or regulatory requirements that need to be resolved?

For our project:

The project deliverable (a new function for syntactic queries on constituency trees) justifying the investment. Additionally, the project's execution became a research subject for an internship.

Data Source Assessment

Examine key aspects of prospect data sources:

- Provenance
- Stability
- Quality
- Sustainability
- Copyright status

For our project we used 'Nestle 1904' because:

- Public domain
- Preexisting XML Treebank with constituency grammar
- Word level compatibility with Bible Online Learner
- Nestle 1904 *de facto* standard for linguistic research

XML input data stability

Typical XML element structure:

```
<tag attribute1="value1" attribute2="value2">text</tag>
```

XML Input Data Stability impact:

- Attribute changes: Orthographic/morphological changes have minimal impact; syntactical changes can significantly alter presentation and query results.
- Tag name changes: Can cause compatibility issues, requiring updates to the conversion tool.
- Tree presentation changes: Affect element arrangement and relationships, potentially altering data interpretation.

Database organisation: node types

Important: Text-Fabric features are attached to nodes

Design questions:

- Which input data elements should translate to nodes?
- Which node types need to be added

For our project:

- Dropped some tags: e.g. the <p> and the <milestone> tags from the LowFat Tree data.
- Added corpus organizational node types that were not explicit in the XML data like 'book', 'chapter', and 'chapter'.
- Added syntactic node types like 'phrase' or 'clause' mirroring the 'wg' nodes.

Database organisation: tokenization

Determines the smallest addressable entity in the text:

- Word
- Letter
- Symbols (example Uruk)

Value creation by data manipulation

Transportation

moving data without changing its fundamental structure or meaning

Translation

improving or clarifying data, making attribute names and values more understandable or standardized

Transformation

adding new, derived, or synthesized attributes and values from the existing data

Benefits of git repositories

GitHub repository:

- Version Tracking
 - Collaboration
 - Backup and Recovery
 - Branching and Merging.
 - Community and Open Source
 - Documentation automation
 - Can easily be 'DOI-ed'
-
- Makes your work visible, accessible and reusable!

Advice Dirk Roorda:
work in a repo
from start-to-finish

Geneology TF Nestle 1904 GNT TF datasets

A long road

Implementation	Source data	Production method
First attempt	Low Fat Tree	Direct XML import using <code>tf.convert.xml</code>
Second attempt	GBI nodes	Using an intermediate relational database with <code>tf.convert.walker</code> and Python scripts
Third attempt: Nestle1904GBI	GBI nodes	Using intermediate 'flat datatables' (stored as .pkl files) with <code>tf.convert.walker</code> and <code>tf.convert.director</code> functions
Fourth attempt: Nestle1904LFT	Low Fat Tree	Using intermediate 'flat datatables' (stored as .pkl files) with <code>tf.convert.walker</code> and <code>tf.convert.director</code> functions
Final attempt: Nestle1904	Low Fat Tree	Direct XML import using (updated) <code>tf.convert.xml</code> and <code>tf.convert.director</code> functions

Method 1: Direct XML Import

This method uses TF's xml-import function and corpus-specific code to convert XML tags into nodes and XML attributes into features

Used as both the initial and the final conversion strategy.

Method 2: Intermediate relational database

This method uses TF's walker function, requiring preprocessing of XML source data stored in a MariaDB database. Each tag-type has its own table, with attributes as fields. The director function extracts and feeds the data to the walker, decoupling the XML structure from the walker's input format.

Method 3: Intermediate Flat Data Tables

A script collects XML data into a pandas DataFrame for each source file, with each `<w>` tag becoming a row and its attributes forming the columns. This converts the structured XML into flat tables with redundancy. The DataFrames are saved as binary pickle files (.pkl). In the second stage, the pickle data is converted into TF format using the `tf.convert.walker` module, guided by the `director` function.

Coding environment

Development Environment

Software Stack

Coding environment: OS impact

File paths separators	back slashes	forward slashes
Home directory	%USERPROFILE%.	tilde (~)
Case handling	case-insensitive	case-insensitive
handling of next line	\r\n	\n

Potential GitHub problems due to OS interactions:

Warning: the following paths have collided (e.g., case-sensitive paths on a case-insensitive filesystem), and only one from the same colliding group is in the working tree.

Open TF environment

Open to all sides:

- Data sources (in our dataset: optional add-on features)
- Additional functionality (in our dataset: view type commands)
- Flexible post processing of resulting data
- ... etc.

Unlocking potentials

Problem: access to data does not give understanding

Mitigation:

- Clear and consistent end-user documentation
- Dense Hyperlinking
- Speeding up learning curve by providing examples

A well-documented dataset with comprehensive metadata allows researchers to easily understand its content, potential and value

Feature documentation

Nestle 1904 GNT - Features

In Text-Fabric, a "feature" refers to attributes associated with nodes type (like words, word groups, or sentences). The features provide additional information specific to the attribute of the nodes.

All features listed by feature name.

The full featureset of this Text-Fabric dataset can also be viewed using different grouping methods:

- Grouped by feature type
 - Node**: the fundamental units or entities in the data model.
 - Edge**: relationships or links, establishing connections between nodes in the data model.
 - Config**: contains the configuration or settings that control the behavior and parameters of the data processing analysis.
- Grouped by feature group:
 - Grid**: features pertaining to the arrangement and organization of the database.
 - Sectional**: features related to structural divisions within the text.
 - Orthographic**: features related to the visual representation of the text.

Orthographic features

These features are related to the visual representation of the text.

Name	Data type	Feature type	Available on nodes	Description	Examples
after	String	Node	word subphrase phrase	All material found after a word (incl. critical signs)	. ;
normalized	String	Node	word subphrase phrase	Normalized form of the surface text	πρὸς
punctuation	String	Node	word subphrase phrase	Punctuations after the word	. ;
text	String	Node	word subphrase phrase	Word as it appears in the text	λόγος θεῶν,
trailer	String	Node	word subphrase phrase	All material found after a word (excl. critical signs)	.
translit	String	Node	word subphrase phrase	Transliteration of the Greek word surface text	estin auton

Nestle 1904 GNT - Feature: punctuation

Data type	Available for node types	Used by viewtypes
String	word subphrase phrase	syntax-view wg-view

Feature: punctuation

punctuation character found after a word. If no punctuation, the feature is not present.

Used for `phrase` or `subphrase`, but only if they consist of one or more characters.

Used by `syntax-view` and `wg-view`:

Unicode codepoint	Frequency
,	9462
;	5717

End-user documentation maintenance

Observation:

Syncing feature documentation with development is labour-intensive and error-prone due to various types of updates, such as:

- Adding or deleting features or changing feature names
- changes in associated node types
- Changes in value domains

repo status **Active**

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.12705876](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12705876)

License **CC BY 4.0**

 tonyjurg/Doc4TF
GitHub

FAIR principles

F
Findable

A
Accessible

I
Interoperable

R
Reusable

<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>

Featured Image: [FAIR data principles](#) by SangyaPundir under [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) license

Published location

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13117911](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13117911)

<https://centerblc.github.io/N1904/>

Thank you!

FACULTY OF
RELIGION
AND THEOLOGY

Q & A
